

CADENAS DE BÚSQUEDA — RSL QOCM

Requerimientos para la Evaluación Ontológica de Ciberseguridad en SCF e IC en la Era Cuántica

Grupo GTI · Universidad del Cauca | Grupo In2Lab · Universidad de Antioquia

1. Cadena de búsqueda base

La siguiente cadena constituyó el punto de partida del protocolo de búsqueda. Fue construida a partir del marco PICOC y sometida a prueba piloto antes de su aplicación definitiva. A partir de esta cadena base se derivaron y adaptaron todas las cadenas específicas para cada fuente de datos, ajustando la sintaxis de operadores, los campos de búsqueda y los filtros propios de cada plataforma, garantizando la equivalencia semántica de los términos en todas las fuentes.

Componente PICOC	Términos empleados
Población (P)	"cyber-physical systems", "CPS", "critical infrastructure"
Intervención (I)	"cybersecurity evaluation model", "ontology evaluation model", "assessment model", "quantum cybersecurity model"
Comparación (C)	"best practices", "comparative analysis", "cybersecurity frameworks"
Resultado (O)	"identify improvement opportunities", "cybersecurity enhancement", "quantum risk assessment"
Contexto (C)	"quantum era", "quantum threats", "critical infrastructure"

CADENA BASE (aplicada en todas las fuentes con adaptación de sintaxis):

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("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure")
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Esta cadena fue ajustada a la sintaxis específica de cada plataforma (IEEE, ACM, ScienceDirect, Scopus, SpringerLink, Google Académico y Literatura Gris), manteniendo la equivalencia semántica de todos sus componentes. Las adaptaciones se presentan en las secciones 2–6 de este documento.

2. IEEE Xplore — Adaptación de la cadena base

Fuente tipo: Base de datos editorial · Modalidad: Advanced Search · Campos: All Metadata · Filtros: Journals · 2020–2026

#	Cadena base	Cadena ajustada a la plataforma	Configuración aplicada
1	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure")	((("All Metadata":cyber-physical systems) AND ("All Metadata":CPS) AND ("All Metadata":cybersecurity evaluation model) AND ("All Metadata":ontology evaluation model) OR ("All Metadata":assessment model) AND ("All Metadata":quantum cybersecurity model) AND ("All Metadata":cybersecurity frameworks) AND ("All Metadata":identify improvement opportunities) OR ("All Metadata":cybersecurity enhancement) OR ("All Metadata":quantum risk assessment) AND ("All Metadata":quantum era) AND ("All Metadata":critical infrastructure))))	Filters: Journals · 2020–2026 · Executed: October 2025

3. ACM Digital Library — Adaptación de la cadena base

Fuente tipo: Base de datos editorial · Modalidad: Advanced Search con operadores de campo · Filtros: E-Publication Date 2020–2025

#	Cadena base	Cadena ajustada a la plataforma	Configuración aplicada
1	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: dimensión cuántica]	[[All: "cyber-physical systems"] OR [All: "cps"]] AND [[All: "quantum era"] OR [All: "quantum threats"] OR [All: "quantum cybersecurity model"] OR [All: "quantum risk assessment"]]	E-Publication Date: 01/01/2020 TO 12/31/2025
2	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: modelo de evaluación]	[[All: "cyber-physical systems"] OR [All: "cps"]] AND [[All: "cybersecurity evaluation model"] OR [All: "ontology evaluation model"] OR [All: "assessment model"]]	E-Publication Date: 01/01/2020 TO 12/31/2025
3	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: IC y marcos]	[[All: "cyber-physical systems"] OR [All: "cps"]] AND [[All: "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure"] OR [All: "critical infrastructure"]] AND [[All: "best practices"] OR [All: "comparative analysis"] OR [All: "cybersecurity frameworks"]]	E-Publication Date: 01/01/2020 TO 12/31/2025
4	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: mejora ciberseguridad]	[All: "cyber-physical systems"] AND [All: "cps"] AND [[All: "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure"] OR [All: "critical infrastructure"]] AND [[All: "identify improvement opportunities"] OR [All: "cybersecurity enhancement"]]	E-Publication Date: 01/01/2020 TO 12/31/2025

4. ScienceDirect — Adaptación de la cadena base

Fuente tipo: Base de datos editorial (Elsevier) · Modalidad: búsqueda por título/resumen/palabras clave · Filtros: Journals · 2020–2026

#	Cadena base	Cadena ajustada a la plataforma	Configuración aplicada
1	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR	("critical infrastructure" OR "cybersecurity in critical infrastructure") AND ("quantum cybersecurity model" OR "quantum risk assessment" OR "quantum threats" OR "quantum era")	Journals · 2020–2026

#	Cadena base	Cadena ajustada a la plataforma	Configuración aplicada
	"cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: dimensión cuántica en IC]		
2	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: modelo + mejora]	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("cybersecurity enhancement")	Journals · 2020–2026
3	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("identify improvement opportunities" OR "cybersecurity enhancement" OR "quantum risk assessment") AND ("quantum era" OR "quantum threats" OR "critical infrastructure") [Foco: modelo + marcos]	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model") AND ("best practices" OR "comparative analysis" OR "cybersecurity frameworks")	Journals · 2020–2026

5. Scopus, SpringerLink y Google Académico — Adaptación vía Publish or Perish

Las siguientes cadenas fueron derivadas de la cadena base y ejecutadas mediante el software Publish or Perish, que permite buscar en Scopus, SpringerLink y Google Académico con sintaxis equivalente.

Fuente de datos	Scopus
Cadena adaptada:	TITLE-ABS-KEY(("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("quantum era" OR "critical infrastructure"))
Derivada de:	Cadena base PICOC — ajuste de sintaxis para motor de búsqueda

Fuente de datos	SpringerLink
Cadena adaptada:	("cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS") AND ("cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model") AND ("best practices" OR "cybersecurity frameworks") AND ("quantum era" OR "critical infrastructure")
Derivada de:	Cadena base PICOC — ajuste de sintaxis para motor de búsqueda

Fuente de datos	Google Académico
Cadena adaptada:	"cyber-physical systems" OR "CPS" AND "cybersecurity evaluation model" OR "ontology evaluation model" OR "assessment model" OR "quantum cybersecurity model" AND "best practices" OR "cybersecurity frameworks" AND "quantum era" OR "critical infrastructure"
Derivada de:	Cadena base PICOC — ajuste de sintaxis para motor de búsqueda

6. Literatura Gris — Búsqueda manual complementaria

Fuente tipo: Fuente complementaria · Modalidad: búsqueda manual en repositorios institucionales · Términos derivados de la cadena base

Repositorio / Fuente	Términos de búsqueda empleados (derivados de la cadena base)
arXiv (cs.CR)	"cyber-physical systems" + "quantum" + "cybersecurity"
NIST Publications	"post-quantum" + "operational technology" + "critical infrastructure"
CISA Resources	"quantum" + "ICS" + "SCADA" + "cybersecurity"
ENISA Reports	"quantum cybersecurity" + "critical infrastructure"
ResearchGate	"cyber-physical systems" + "quantum era" + "ontology" + "cybersecurity"
Google Scholar (gris)	"quantum cybersecurity model" + "CPS" + "critical infrastructure" filetype:pdf

Nota metodológica: Todas las adaptaciones mantienen la equivalencia semántica de la cadena base PICOC. Los filtros uniformes aplicados fueron: tipo de publicación (Journals) y período temporal (2020–2026). La búsqueda se ejecutó hasta enero de 2026.